

Studies on Tin(IV) Complexes of Some Monohydroxamic Acids

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Abstract: A number of hexacoordinated dichloro bis(hydroxamato) tin(IV) complexes of the general formula R_2SnCl_2 have been prepared from $SnCl_4$ and hydroxamic acids, RH , where $RH = R'CONR''OH$ with $R' = C_6H_5$, 2-(OH)- C_6H_4 , 2-I- C_6H_4 , 3, 5-(NO_2) $_2$ - C_6H_3 and $R'' = H, C_6H_5$, 2- CH_3 - C_6H_4 , 3- CH_3 - C_6H_4 , 4- CH_3 - C_6H_4 , 4-Cl- C_6H_4 . Several physical measurements such as thermogravimetric analysis, conductance, electronic, ir, PMR and mass spectra have been carried out and the results are discussed in terms of structure and bonding of the complexes. The complexes have been found to be octahedral with two chlorine atoms *cis* to each other and the hydroxamate ions acting as bidentate ligands.

HYDROXAMIC acids are weak organic acids¹ with a wide variety of applications including use as commercial floatation reagents in extraction metallurgy, inhibitors for copper corrosion, antifungal agents, pharmaceuticals, food additives, and in nuclear fuel processing. One of the characteristics of hydroxamic acids is their ability to form stable complexes with many metals which forms the basis for their usefulness as analytical reagents². Many metal complexes of synthetic monohydroxamic acids, especially those of iron(III), are also potentially biologically active^{3,4}. We have been interested in both the analytical chemistry^{5,6} and complex chemistry metals, especially with both inorganic and organic tin, and have made a preliminary report⁷. In the present paper, we wish to report a detailed investigation on the tin(IV) chloride complexes of benzohydroxamic acid (BHAH), 2-hydroxybenzohydroxamic acid [2-(OH)BHAAH], N-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid (PBHAAH), N-2-methylphenylbenzohydroxamic acid (2-MePBHAAH), N-3-methylphenylbenzohydroxamic acid (3-MePBHAAH), N-4-methylphenylbenzohydroxamic acid (4-MePBHAAH), N-4-chlorophenylbenzohydroxamic acid (4-ClPBHAAH), N-phenyl-2-iodobenzo hydroxamic acid (P-2-IBHAAH) and N-phenyl-3, 5-dinitrobenzohydroxamic acid [P-3, 5-(NO_2) $_2$ BHAAH].

Experimental

Reagents and Chemicals :

The hydroxamic acids have been prepared by methods available in the literature². All solvents and chemicals were of reagent grade quality. Benzene was dried by refluxing over freshly cut sodium metal for 48 hr. Methanol was dried by refluxing over magnesium turnings for 48 hr, nitromethane was dried over anhydrous $CaCl_2$ for 72 hr, and all solvents were distilled prior to use.

Preparation of R_2SnCl_2 Complexes :

The tin(IV) hydroxamato complexes, R_2SnCl_2 ($RH =$ hydroxamic acid), were prepared by adding a 1-2% ethanolic solution of the required hydroxamic acid (2.5-3.0 molar ratio) to an ice-cold solution of $SnCl_4$ or $SnCl_2$ (containing *ca.* 0.1-0.5 g Sn) in a volume of 200 ml containing 4-6% conc. HCl, when the compounds were precipitated. After allowing to stand for one-half hr, the compounds were filtered, washed with ice-cold water and air dried; they were then recrystallized from a water acetone mixture except $(BHA)_2SnCl_2$ and $[2-(OH)BHA]_2SnCl_2$. The latter two were recrystallized from a water-ethanol mixture containing few drops of conc. HCl, because of their high solubility in acetone. The recrystallized products were dried in vacuum. The yields were essentially quantitative and all compounds were white crystalline substances except the $[P-3,5-(NO_2)_2BHA]_2SnCl_2$ which was slightly brownish. The analytical data and the melting points are given in Table 1. Tin was determined by decomposition of the compounds with conc. HNO_3 and then igniting to SnO_2 and chlorine was determined as silver chloride. Nitrogen was determined by the Jadavpur University Microanalytical Service.

Physical Measurements :

A Chevenard-Joumier Thermobalance (ADAMEL) was used for thermogravimetric analyses. A Phillips conductivity measuring bridge PR-9500 was used for the measurements of conductivities. Electronic spectra were taken with a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer using quartz cells. Infrared spectra were recorded as Nujol mulls on KBr discs and on polyethylene plates or as KBr pellets, using a Perkin-Elmer 621, Beckman IR-12 and Perkin-Elmer 337 infrared spectrometers. A Beckman IR-11 spectrometer was used for recording the far infrared spectra. All

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE TIN(IV) COMPLEXES

S. No.	Compound	M.P.(°C)	Elemental Analysis			Decomposition Temp. Range (°C)	Molar Con- ductance (ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹) in * Methanol
			Sn	Found/ Calcd. % N	Cl		
1.	(BHA) ₂ SnCl ₂	260 (dec.)	25.52 25.71	6.10 6.07	15.43 15.36	260-526	195
2.	[2-(OH)BHA] ₂ SnCl ₂	250 (dec.)	23.99 24.05	5.75 5.68	14.46 14.36	250-530	193
3.	(PBHA) ₂ SnCl ₂	217	19.24 19.34	4.61 4.56	11.63 11.55	293-576	384
4.	(2-MePBHA) ₂ SnCl ₂	227	18.55 18.49	4.47 4.36	11.12 11.05	288-562	360
5.	(3-MePBHA) ₂ SnCl ₂	203	18.51 18.49	4.41 4.36	11.21 11.05	297-530	388
6.	(4-MePBHA) ₂ SnCl ₂	208	18.43 18.49	4.39 4.36	11.15 11.05	264-528	372
7.	(4-CIPBHA) ₂ SnCl ₂	220	17.27 17.42	4.02 4.01	20.91 20.80	300-590	388
8.	(P-2-IBHA) ₂ SnCl ₂	200	13.77 13.72	3.16 3.24	-	298-567	392
9.	[P-3,5-(NO ₂) ₂ BHA] ₂ SnCl ₂	219	14.91 14.96	10.30 10.59	9.01 8.93	289-600	376

spectra were calibrated using a polystyrene film with respect to the 1601 or 1028 cm⁻¹ band (except those taken with Beckman IR-11). PMR spectra were recorded using Varian T-60 and Varian A60A NMR spectrometers. Deuteriochloroform (99.8%D) and deuterioacetone (99.7%D) were used as solvents and tetramethylsilane was used as internal standard for taking the PMR spectra. Mass spectra were obtained using AEI MS-902 mass spectrometer at 70 eV.

Results and Discussion

Thermogravimetric Studies :

The thermogravimetric analysis was initially undertaken in order to investigate whether the complexes obtained from tin(II) and tin(IV) chlorides prepared under the same conditions were the same, and it was found that the complexes obtained from both tin(II) and tin(IV) chlorides were the same from a study of their thermal behaviors. The decomposition temperatures of tin complexes as obtained from the thermogravimetric curves are given in Table 1. In each case the temperatures were raised to 700° and all are converted to SnO₂. The complexes decompose in such a way that no intermediates are formed during decomposition.

Conductance Studies :

Conductance studies of the complexes have been made in nitromethane and methanol. All the complexes are found to be non-electrolytes in nitromethane having λ₀ values of 0.9-3.2 ohm⁻¹cm²mole⁻¹ for 1×10⁻³ molar solutions; the molar conductance values at infinite dilution (λ₀) in methanol are collected in Table 1. In the case of methanol as solvent, the molar conductances (λ₀) have been calculated from the resistances corresponding to different concentrations of the

complexes and were then plotted against the √c (where c=concentration) and finally extrapolated to zero concentration to find the molar conductances at infinite dilution, λ₀. The λ₀ values of the complexes R₂SnCl₂ (RH=ligand) obtained were between 360 and 392 ohm⁻¹cm²mole⁻¹, except for the complexes (BHA)₂SnCl₂ and [2-(OH)BHA]₂SnCl₂. For the latter two complexes the λ₀ values obtained by the above procedure are 195 and 193 ohm⁻¹cm²mole⁻¹, respectively. Since the complexes were found to be non-electrolytes in nitromethane and electrolytes in methanol, the results might be explained by assuming solvolysis of the complexes in methanol. Two kinds of solvolysis may take place as shown in eqs. (1a-1b) and (2a-2b).

The λ₀ values in methanol for 1:1 electrolytes of the type as shown in eq. (1a) fall in the range 80-115 ohm⁻¹cm²mole⁻¹, and for 2:1 electrolytes as shown in eq. (1b) fall in the range 160-220 ohm⁻¹cm²mole⁻¹. On the other hand, the equivalent conductance values of H⁺ and Cl⁻ ions at infinite dilution in methanol are 141.8 and 51.3 ohm⁻¹cm²mole⁻¹; thus, the calculated λ₀ value for HCl in methanol is 193.1 ohm⁻¹cm²mole⁻¹. If the solvolysis had taken place according to eq. (2b), the conductance value for 2HCl would be 2×193.1=386.2 ohm⁻¹cm²mole⁻¹, and the values obtained for all complexes (except (BHA)₂SnCl₂ and [2-(OH)BHA]₂SnCl₂) are in the range 360 to 392 ohm⁻¹cm²mole⁻¹, which is reasonably close to the calculated

value from equivalent conductances. The λ_0 values of $(\text{BHA})_2\text{SnCl}_2$ and $[\text{2-(OH)BHA}]_2\text{SnCl}_2$ are approximately equal to the λ_0 value of HCl in methanol; this value is also comparable to the λ_0 value of the 2:1 electrolytes according to eq. (1b). But the latter assumption may be discarded by considering that the solutions of all the complexes in methanol-water mixtures were found to be acidic. It may, therefore, be concluded that the complexes $(\text{BHA})_2\text{SnCl}_2$ and $[\text{2-(OH)BHA}]_2\text{SnCl}_2$ undergo solvolysis in methanol according to eq. (2a), and all others undergo solvolysis according to eq. (2b). At first sight, this behavior seems surprising, but may not be unreasonable since the ligands BHAH and 2-(OH)BHAH are somewhat different and their complexes may behave differently, which was also noticed in the mass spectral studies (*vide infra*).

Electronic Spectra :

The electronic spectra of all ligands and their tin(IV) hydroxamate complexes, R_2SnCl_2 , except the ligands BHAH and 2-(OH)BHAH and their complexes, have been measured in benzene against a solvent blank in the range 280 to 600 nm. The latter two ligands and their complexes were too insoluble for such measurements. Absorptions in the range 280 to 350 nm were negligibly small for both the ligands and their corresponding complexes. Our results are in conformity with those reported for $\text{Sn}(\text{acac})_2\text{X}_2$ ¹⁰ and $\text{Sn}(\text{IV})$ complexes with polydentate N,O-ligands¹¹.

Infrared Spectra :

The infrared spectra in the range 4000 to 70 cm^{-1} for the complexes have been measured along with those of the ligands. A notable feature of the infrared spectra of the complexes is the absence of the ligand stretching modes for both "free" and hydrogen bonded O-H in the ranges of 3030 to 3240 cm^{-1} and 2740 to 2900 cm^{-1} , indicating the replacement of the O-H hydrogen by the metal. The $\nu(\text{N-H})$ modes of both $(\text{BHA})_2\text{SnCl}_2$ and $[\text{2-(OH)BHA}]_2\text{SnCl}_2$ were found at 3280 and 3270 cm^{-1} respectively; these values remain almost unaffected compared to those of the ligands.

Another distinctive feature of the spectra is the shifting of the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching frequencies in the complexes from those observed in the ligands. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ mode in the ligands is shifted to 1615-1595 cm^{-1} , owing to hydrogen bonding with N-OH of the ligands. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ values of both ligands and their corresponding metal complexes, along with the shifts, are given in Table 2. In the complexes the carbonyl frequencies lie in the region 1531-1508 cm^{-1} , shifted 70-100 cm^{-1} to lower energy, indicating $\text{C}=\text{O}$ coordination. Similar results have been observed with the acetylacona-

tes¹² or other β -diketonates¹³. Another important feature of the spectra was the appearance of new bands due to $\nu(\text{Sn-Cl})$ and $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$ modes of vibrations in the lower frequency range. The $\nu(\text{Sn-Cl})$ mode is reported to occur over the wide region of 365-285 cm^{-1} ^{10,11,13-15}, and we have found a group of new bands of medium to strong intensity in the region 347-315 cm^{-1} (Table 2). The stretching frequencies of Sn-O bonds in the pyridine N-oxide complexes of organic and inorganic tin(IV) appear in the region 400-300 cm^{-1} ¹⁶ and in DMSO complexes of tin(IV), the Sn-O vibrations are assigned to 500-400 cm^{-1} bands¹⁷. In various acetylacetonates of tin(IV) this mode is assigned to 461-404 cm^{-1} bands¹⁸, and in $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{CHCl}_2\text{CO}_2)_2$, the 410 cm^{-1} band is assigned to Sn-O vibration¹⁹. We have found consistently a band of medium to strong intensity in each of the complexes in the region 455-400 cm^{-1} (Table 2), which may be assigned to Sn-O vibrations.

For all these complexes, two $\nu(\text{Sn-Cl})$ vibrations are observed for each complex; since there are two bands due to $\nu(\text{Sn-Cl})$ mode, all the complexes studied must be octahedral with two Cl atoms *cis* to each other, as shown below.

$\text{R}' = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5, 2\text{-(OH)C}_6\text{H}_4, 2\text{-1-C}_6\text{H}_4, 3, 5\text{-(NO}_2)_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_3,$
 $\text{R}'' = \text{H, C}_6\text{H}_5, 2\text{-Me C}_6\text{H}_4, 3\text{-MeC}_6\text{H}_4, 4\text{-MeC}_6\text{H}_4,$
 $4\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4.$

PMR Spectra :

The proton magnetic resonance spectra of the R_2SnCl_2 complexes do not differ much from those of the corresponding ligands except that the signals due to NOH protons which were found to occur in the regions $\delta = 9.03$ to 10.40 ppm were lacking. The methyl group signals are all singlets and the aromatic proton signals are complex, and both are observed in the same positions in their corresponding ligands. No 119, 117 Sn...¹H couplings were found in the spectra.

TABLE 2—VARIOUS GROUP FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹)

S. No.	Compound	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})^a$ in		$\Delta\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})^b$	$\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{Cl})^a$		$\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{O})^a$
		Compounds	ligands				
1.	(BHA) ₂ SnCl ₂	1508 s	1600 s	-92	323 s	315 s	425 s
2.	[2-(OH)BHA] ₂ SnCl ₂	1508 s	1590 s	-82	329 msh	322 m	400 m
3.	(PBHA) ₂ SnCl ₂	1515 s	1615 s	-100	332 s	325 s	438 s
4.	(2-MePBHA) ₂ SnCl ₂	1528 s	1600 s	-72	344 s	332 s	450 s
5.	(3-MePBHA) ₂ SnCl ₂	1525 s	1595 s	-70	347 s	330 s	455 m
6.	(4-MePBHA) ₂ SnCl ₂	1530 s	1600 s	-70	332 s	325 ssh	420 m
7.	(4-ClPBHA) ₂ SnCl ₂	1521 s	1592 s	-71	344 msh	335 s	430 m
8.	(P-2-IBHA) ₂ SnCl ₂	1530 s	1615 s	-85	347 ssh	338 s	421 s
9.	[P-3,5-(NO ₂ BHA) ₂ SnCl ₂	1531 s	1615 s	-84	340 msh	331 s	421 m

^as=strong, sh=shoulder, m=medium. ^bMinus sign indicates shifts towards lower frequencies.

Mass Spectral Study :

The mass spectra of six tin(IV) hydroxamate complexes, namely (BHA)₂SnCl₂, (PBHA)₂SnCl₂, (2-MePBHA)₂SnCl₂, (3-MePBHA)₂SnCl₂, (4-MePBHA)₂SnCl₂, (4-ClPBHA)₂SnCl₂, were recorded at a probe temperature of 230° using 70 eV electrons. All the spectra were characterized by polyisotopic "clusters" at different m/e ratios, especially at the high m/e values. The mass spectra of all the complexes [except (BHA)₂SnCl₂] show the molecular ions as the highest peaks, and the molecular weights obtained from the mass spectral data were the same as the formula weights. In the case of (BHA)₂SnCl₂ no peaks higher than m/e=260 have been observed, whereas the formula weight is 462. The peak at m/e=260 for (BHA)₂SnCl₂ may be assigned to ClSnOC₇H₅⁺ ion. The results indicate that the five complexes (PBHA)₂SnCl₂, (2-MePBHA)₂SnCl₂, (3-MePBHA)₂SnCl₂, (4-MePBHA)₂SnCl₂ and (4-ClPBHA)₂SnCl₂ are somewhat more stable than the (BHA)₂SnCl₂ complex under the conditions of the experiments. The fragmentation patterns follow a regular trend reflecting successive loss of chlorine atoms, methyl groups (where they are present) and even loss of a ligand. In some cases, it was found that C₆H₅CO⁺, C₆H₅N⁺, CH₃C₆H₄N⁺ or ClC₆H₄N⁺ ions are lost, leading to complete decomposition to Sn⁺. In addition, in some cases a rearrangement leading to the formation of SnC₆H₅⁺ ion had taken place. The spectral features of (2-MePBHA)₂SnCl₂, (3-MePBHA)₂SnCl₂ and (4-MePBHA)₂SnCl₂ are very similar, whereas the spectra of the (PBHA)₂SnCl₂ and (4-ClPBHA)₂SnCl₂ are somewhat different from these. The spectral characteristics of (BHA)₂SnCl₂ is significantly different from all the others; first, it does not have any molecular ion peak, and second, the decomposition route which

could be deduced from the spectra was different, since the ligand itself is somewhat different. The complex also melted with decomposition whereas the others did not.

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